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GLOBALIZATION OF MODEST FASHION: ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATIONS AND INSIGHTS FROM CONTEMPORARY MUSLIM CIVILIZATION

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This study investigates how increasing cultural interaction due to globalization and technology imprints a considerable impact on the modest fashion industry. Emphasizing the role of digital technology and global marketing, this study specifically highlights the influence of contemporary Muslim civilization on the industry. This study uses a systematic literature review to examine the impact and intersections between globalization, the modest fashion industry, entrepreneurial innovations, and contemporary Muslim society. The findings highlight that the emergence of e-commerce and digital marketing are not the only factors that influence the industry. It emphasizes that the factors such as religiosity, culture, and market differences due to specific ethno-geographic differences are the important precursors that represent the influence of modern Muslim civilization on current trends and standards of the industry.

Keywords: Modest Fashion, Entrepreneurial Innovations, Contemporary Muslim Civilization, Digital Marketing, Market Trends

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1. Introduction

Modest fashion has a long history and is centred around the practice of covering the body in line with various cultural and religious customs globally. Modest fashion has origins in Islamic teachings and religious practices and has transformed in many ways over the course of time. It has evolved from simply local and traditional wear for both men and women to modest wear of various cultures and modern fashion trends. Customers from different parts of the world now seek to dress more modestly and have started to appreciate the beauty and ethics associated with the styles (Lewis & Almila, 2020). The modest fashion industry has remained on the upward trend, expanding its growth beyond conventional parameters. In the expanding and diversifying market, modern modest wear businesses in Malaysia need to adapt to the market to reap the benefits of potential growth.

The most recent report of the Global Islamic Economy Report by Dinar Standard (2023) indicates that Muslim expenditure on clothing and footwear increased by 4%- and 8%-year over-year between 2022 and 2023. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) countries alone imported an estimated US\$37.1 billion of fashion and apparel. The global Muslim consumer expenditure for modest clothing and footwear is expected to grow to US\$428 billion by 2027 with a CAGR of 6% (Liaqat, 2023).

Traditional markets such as Iran, Turkey and Pakistan are still important but newer markets in southeast Asia, Africa and even America are growing. China is the largest supplier of modest wear to OIC countries exporting clothes and footwear of US\$ 18.6 billion to these countries for the period of 2022 to 2023. The modern customer is more aware of their consumption choices, and they want to buy and consume products that are sustainably produced and marketed through online channels.

1.1. The role of globalization in shaping modest fashion industry

The rise and widespread adoption of modest fashion are significantly influenced by the phenomenon of globalization. The interchange of modest fashion cultures has been facilitated by the advancement of the digital era and the integration of worldwide economies. International markets have also allowed modest fashion brands to expand their product lines and target an even larger customer base due to globalization. This global reach has been enhanced even further using social media platforms in marketing and brand development in fashion (Bucar, 2023).

Globalizing modest fashion has not only influenced the market but also fostered a deeper understanding of cultural differences. Both Islamic and non-Islamic societies have embraced

the integration of Islamic clothing into modern fashion. This highlights the significance of modest fashion in the exchange of cultures in today's interconnected world (Radwan *et al.*, 2019).

1.2. The Intersection of Entrepreneurial Innovations and Islamic Civilization in Modest Fashion

The modest fashion industry has experienced several entrepreneurial advancements, especially regarding the increased call for religious clothing and dressing. These innovations include the emergence of 'modest fashion' e-shops, the formulation of appropriate marketing approaches, and the diversification of fashionable clothing collections to represent different degrees of Islamic dressing (Radwan *et al.*, 2019). Current entrepreneurial innovations in the sector depict how the founders of the modest fashion industry were able to overcome the challenges of balancing religious and cultural market appeal with globalization.

Furthermore, incorporating Islamic civilization's values and teachings has always been at the heart of modest fashion entrepreneurship. The business strategies of modest fashion brands have been shaped by the principles of the Islamic dress code, Islamic ethics of dress, Islamic business management, and social responsibility. These values have not only shaped the manufacturing and assembly strategies, but they have also influenced how this industry addresses social issues such as sustainability and accountability.

1.3. Theoretical Framework

1.3.1. Globalization as a theory

Globalization, as a concept, refers to the integration of people, companies, and countries, with one other through the flow of capital, products, ideas, information, and services. According to Giddens (1991), globalisation is the affiliation of far-flung places, whereby what happens in different parts of the world affects happenings in other parts, and vice versa. Steger (2017) then extends and expands this definition of globalization to present it as 'a complex process of social relations that create, deepen, widen and expand interconnectedness'.

These definitions also introduce the notions of interdependence, intertwined relationships and networks, and the flow of people, commodities, and information across the borders of states. The theory offers the guideline that helps to shed light on how the economic and cultural processes of the global level connect to the local processes, and vice versa, how the local processes affect the global ones. It also reflects upon such processes in terms of

identity, power, and cultural circulation, which makes it relevant to talk about fashion and consumption.

1.3.2. Relation to the Fashion Industry

Globalization has played a pivotal role in the fashion industry, where styles and trends have been spread across different countries and regions, giving fashion a more cosmopolitan and varied character. Appadurai (1996) extends the idea of flows, which identifies how cultural items like fashion are distributed and consumed around the world and the dynamics of media, migration, and technology. This circulation has resulted in the integration of different aspects of different cultures in fashion known as cultural hybridity and has created a global fashion industry that meets the different cultural demands of the people across the world (Kraidy, 2006). These processes have also affected the fashion industry and its subsector, the modest fashion industry. Media and the internet made it possible for the market of modest fashion to expand beyond the core Muslim audience and attract consumers who seek fashionable clothes but do not want to reveal too much skin. This globalization of modest fashion is also made possible by the opportunities for exportation and the movement of designers and businesspeople across borders and different cultures (Lewis & Almila, 2020).

1.3.3. Entrepreneurship in Islamic Perspective

Islamic business entrepreneurship is grounded in the Islamic culture and faith that envision business and economic activity as being conducted in a moral and ethical way for the benefit of the society. Gümüşay, (2015) has done a significant work on the meaning of Islamic entrepreneurship and describes it as the act of engaging in business activities that are Shariah compliant. This encompasses the observance of ethical principles like the ban on misleading, the concept of justice and the rejection of *riba* (usury). The term *halal* is not only restricted to food but also covers all the business activities to make a particular business compatible with religious guidelines in Islam.

Hassan & Hippler, (2014) go further in pointing out that Islamic business is not only about the accumulation of capital but also about giving back to society and attaining divine contentment. It also becomes a motivation for those young and creative minds to come up with products that are not only useful but also conform to Islamic standards of dressing and being ethical in business.

1.3.4. Entrepreneurship of Modest Fashion

Therefore, the role of entrepreneurship is pivotal for the growth and advancement of the emerging niche, such as the modest fashion industry. Ahmed, (2024) pointed out that the emergence of modest fashion brands is due to the new generation of Muslims who are using the internet selling platforms to meet the increased demand for modest and fashionable clothes. These are usually individuals who start businesses to offer clothes that do not conform to the usual fashion, due to their cultural or religious beliefs.

Al-Dajani and Marlow (2013) have pointed out that, women are playing an active role in the growth of modest fashion industry and many women have been gaining employment and income through this business. These are not only influencing the industry but also breaking cultural norms by being active participants in the global market through entrepreneurship.

1.3.5. Impact of Religion and Culture on Consumer Buying Decisions

Religious and cultural beliefs are important factors that help shape the market consumer in the modest fashion industry. According to Osanlou & Rezaei (2024) Muslim consumers look for products that are halal compliant and these are products that are produced and consumed in accordance with Islamic principles which include modesty, purity, and the ethical consumption of goods. This has created a niche market of modest fashion, in which the consumers are not only in search of apparels that adhere to their religious beliefs but also apparels that are made ethically and sustainably.

Radwan *et al.* (2019) also describes how these modest fashion brands have addressed such consumer demands by integrating Islamic values into their operations. These also involve the upkeep of transparent supply chains, participation in philanthropic activities, and the genuineness of Halal certification. The ethical and environmental concerns of these businesses are also appealing to clients from various religious backgrounds, suggesting that it is not only Muslims who value these efforts.

1.3.6. Relation between Culture, Religion, and Global Market Trends

One of the most important features of the modest fashion industry is that it reflects the culture and religion of many people around the world and trends in the global market. Bucar (2023) postulates that due to globalization, cultural and religious practices such as the practice of modest fashion, has gone viral. This has resulted in a combination of the Islamic dress code with the current fashion trends that have made the clothes popular to a global market.

Slater & Demangeot (2021) point out that this integration is not without problems, in which modest fashion brands can face problems due to cultural differences and different perceptions of the concept of modesty. But it also has its advantages and potential for further development, given that these brands have an audience around the world who appreciate fashion and cultural identity. From the discussion of cultural and religious aspects of modest fashion this industry is far from being stable and homogenous in the context of globalization.

1.4. Objectives of the study

The primary objectives of this study are threefold:

- a) To evaluate the impact of globalization on the modest fashion industry

This study seeks to examine the impact of globalization on the development and advancement of the modest fashion sector. It examines how global market conditions, cultural interactions, and emerging technology have influenced the industry.

- b) *To analyse the developing entrepreneurial patterns in the industry.*

This study examines the impact of digital technology, e-commerce, and worldwide marketing techniques on the growth of the sector.

- c) *To acquire significant information regarding the modest fashion industry from contemporary Muslim societies.*

This study investigates the influence of contemporary Muslim civilization on the modest fashion industry and its ongoing impact. To accomplish this, the text examines the fundamental concepts of Islamic injunctions, cultural traditions, and contributions to research that influence the future of the sector.

2. Methodology

2.1. Systematic Literature Review Approach

To achieve the research objectives, the systematic literature review approach was used in this study. This method involves several steps in searching for appropriate literature, appraising, and integrating the information. According to M. Petticrew and H. Roberts (2006), this methodology is useful for the purpose of ascertaining the current state of knowledge and identifying the plausible research agendas that can fill the existing gaps.

2.2. Criteria for Selecting Literature

In this regard, this study aims at focusing on the literature by applying certain criteria for inclusion and exclusion. The first criterion is primarily driven by the type of publication, which focuses on articles, books, and reports that have appeared in scholarly journals. However, the priority is given to those works that are related to the topics of globalization, modest fashion, and the Islamic world. This study also explores research that specifically focuses on the examination of entrepreneurship within the context of the modest fashion business. It is noted that to exclude unreliable sources, papers before the specified date, and articles not relevant to the study goals, exclusion criteria are used.

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis Methods

The method of data collection in this study is a library-based search in the electronic databases Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Scopus. Thus, the following keywords are used: “modest fashion”, “globalization”, “Islamic civilization”, “entrepreneurship”, “digital marketing”. Synthesis entails reviewing and integrating the information gathered from different sources to establish relationships with other information. This research provides a genuine and objective angle on the link between globalization and the industry of modest attire in contemporary settings. Moreover, it reveals the role of entrepreneurial solutions in this case and the impact of the Islamic culture on the field.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Origin and Evolution of Modest Fashion

The concept of modest fashion, which is clothing that does not reveal so much of the body as to be appropriate in some cultures and religions, has its roots in ancient societies. Modesty in dressing is one of the most important and enduring tenets of the Islamic tradition that has its roots in the most ancient times. Modesty in the Islamic tradition can be discussed based on the primary sources of Islam i.e., the Quran and the Prophetic traditions (Hadith). Contrary to the current perception and based on some Religio-cultural interpretations, the concept of modesty that is seen in the clothing is not unique to Muslim-majority societies but has been observed in Christian, Jewish, and other religious groups, in addition to reflecting the culture of decency and propriety.

In the twentieth century, there were some shifts in the meaning of the concept of modesty and the ways it is being implemented in Islamic societies. When modern nation-states

and globalization emerged, traditional dress codes gradually intermingled with modern/nontraditional fashion trends. These interactions have created a new style that is a combination of the traditional Islamic way of dressing with the modern design needs of the newly awakened fashion conscious Muslimahs (Iftaqar, 2024). The return of the hijab and other similar clothing items as fashion accessories rather than merely as symbols of religious compliance has been another significant change, which can be attributed to the fact that people have started adopting a more personal and creative approach towards dressing modestly.

3.2. Tenacious Growth

In the last few decades, modest fashion has made significant progress in popularity and general recognition. In the 1980s and 1990s, the concept of modest fashion was mostly a niche segment within the fashion industry, providing a restricted range of fashionable choices for women who wanted to dress modestly. But the industry experienced a leap in the beginning of the twenty first century due to the emergence of the new media and the internet, which helped spread fashion worldwide (Muturi, 2024). It was during this time that designers and brands that focused on the needs of Muslim women began to appear, creating clothes that were both fashionable and modest.

Another important step towards the development of modest fashion was the holding of the first international modest fashion weeks in Istanbul, London, and Dubai. These events gave a chance to modest fashion designers to present their works on the international level, gain media coverage, and expand the range of people interested in the industry. Furthermore, the integration of modest fashion into mainstream fashion weeks such as New York and Paris fashion weeks underscored acceptance of modest fashion as a valid sector in the global fashion business.

3.3. Expansion in Global Markets

Globalization has spurred the modest fashion industry's growth in global markets, expanding its recognition beyond countries with a Muslim majority. Globalization, the integration of markets, cultures, and societies, has expanded the concept of modest fashion beyond cultural and geographical barriers (Bucar, 2023). The internet is particularly helpful in this process, as is social media, which helped the modest fashion representatives find their audience and create a community of people who appreciate the concept of modesty in fashion.

The increasing demand from Muslim consumers, who have more purchasing power and are seeking fashion that suits their needs, has also propelled the shift to global markets. The Halal economy, defined as a broad spectrum of products and services demanded by Muslim consumers, is responsible for this. This has not only made affordable and more appropriate fashion pieces available to consumers, but it has also helped expand the industry by capturing the attention of consumers who are not only Muslim but who also seek to make responsible fashion choices (Radwan *et al.*, 2019).

3.4. Cross-Cultural Interactions and Adaptations

Despite some limitations, globalization, in some ways, for example, in the case of the small fashion industry, has made a significant contribution to the popularization and support of internationalization and development. The increase of globalization has a positive effect on small fashion businesses and their products because they are affected by rising patterns and values. This has caused the mixing of many cultures, which has given rise to a wide variety of stylistic possibilities that are versatile. For example, many fashion designers in the western world have incorporated modern style and fabrics from western fashion but at the same time respect the decency that has been put in place by Islamic standards (Radwan *et al.*, 2019). This has helped firms to open new opportunities and expand into different sectors and markets hence promoting the establishment of a competitive and diverse market. However, it is noteworthy that designers of “modest” fashion should also consider cultural restraints while at the same time striving to develop new market niches for this type of clothing.

As much as the hijab is part of modest fashion all over the world, particularly in the Muslim countries, it is not a requirement in some of these countries. This has led to the emergence of enhanced designs, which are now more accepting of society’s diversity in an effort to address the needs of people who need discretion around the globe. The cultural and religious contact between people from different parts of the world is also increasingly increasing, and they are now very sensitive to each other. The continued growth of modest fashion sales also points to greater consumer tolerance for multiculturalism and cultural differences among the non-Muslim population. It has not only helped expand the market of adequate clothes but has also changed people and their perception of ‘modesty’ not just in religious terms but a trend or a standard.

3.5. Entrepreneurial Innovations in Modest Fashion Industry

The modern fashion industry of modest dressing has experienced significant growth and innovation primarily from businesspeople. These innovations have not only enhanced the market but have also brought about the modest fashion within an easier and attractive reach to other people around the world. This section looks at the achievements that some of the companies that offer modest fashion and the influence of e-commerce and digital marketing.

3.6. Real Life Examples of Brand Success

The present research investigates the leading modest fashion brands in detail.

There are some brands in the niche of modest dress that have gained significant success in the market and can be considered as leaders in this sphere considering their unique business approaches and target audience knowledge. Among them, we can mention Modanisa, a Turkey based online store that now offers clothes for the most conservative clients all over the world. This is because Modanisa has a wide variety of products to offer its customers, and it targets the various clients within the modest fashion niche. The brand has also endeavoured to offer quality products at the lowest price possible, which has also helped it to expand its market share (*Modanisa: The Transformative Power of Modest Fashion*, 2020).

Another major participant in the market of ethical fashion is Haute Hijab, a company based in the United States which was created by Melanie Elturk. Haute Hijab has achieved its customer base due to its promise of quality and classy apparels. It has also had a great effort in establishing a good community for its brands in the social media and other interactive platforms. This has created a unique brand image for Haute Hijab that caters for the modern Muslim woman who is fashion conscious (Good, 2024).

Another example includes The Modist, a Dubai-born brand that offered luxury clothes for the fashion-conscious, but modest woman. The Modist was one of the online platforms that provided luxury clothing for modesty and were sourced from both mainstream and up-and-coming designers. The brand offered the product to a select demographic of the upper class who are interested in fashionable yet conservative clothing. The case of the Modist also suggests the opportunities of the segment of the modest fashion that can be targeted at different segments, including those who are interested in luxury. This company showed a considerable expansion and became very famous in a short span of time. However, during the Covid-19 pandemic this company couldn't survive due to global crisis, and it had to shut down its operations. (Paracha, 2020).

3.7. Tactics for Global Market Entry and Growth

Many strategies have been adopted to ensure the expansion of modest fashion brands across the globe due to some factors that affect the expansion process. There are two main techniques that organizations employ to cater for the diverse cultures of different societies; these are localization, where an organization modifies their products and promotional techniques to fit the cultural and religious beliefs of a given society. For instance, Modanisa has opened markets in several countries such as the United States and the United Kingdom by providing clothes that are in compliance with the country's decency laws and also marketing in different languages (*Modanisa: The Transformative Power of Modest Fashion*, 2020).

Another successful approach has been partnerships with local opinion leaders and celebrities in the case of brands that have been experimenting with entering the new markets of modest fashion. These collaborations assist brands to gain credibility and reach out to the local consumers. For instance, Haute Hijab, a Muslimah fashion company, has relied on Muslim influencers to advertise its products and reach out to more people. This strategy has been quite effective in markets such as the United States where the Muslim population is heterogeneous and fragmented (Cummings, 2021).

The fourth key area of consideration in the context of internationalisation of modest fashion brands is the aspect of shipping and distribution. Some of the brands that have emerged in the market today like The Modist have ensured that they have proper supply chain networks so that they can be able to deliver their products to the respective customers within the shortest time possible. This capability not only benefits the customers but also enables the brands to challenge the conventional fashion retailers who also provide similar services (Evops, 2024).

3.8. Use of Internet, Online Portals and Social Networking Sites

The advancement in technology such as e-commerce has been a boost to the modest fashion as it eliminates the middleman and gives the clothes a worldwide market. Current websites such as Modanisa and the Modist have benefited from this movement by enabling easy-to-navigate websites and mobile applications. Common elements of these platforms include product descriptions, beautiful images, and customer reviews, which assist consumers in their decision making about what to buy (Usher, 2018).

Social media has also contributed to growth of Modest fashion brands in a big way. Sites such as Instagram, Face book or You tube are among the most crucial tools through which brands can display their products, interact with the consumers and increase their visibility. For instance, Haute Hijab remains active on Instagram where it posts new products, styling blogs

and other information about the company and its products. This not only creates traffic for brand's e-commerce site, but it also turns its followers into a family (*The Impact of Social Media on Modest Fashion, Deenbiscuit, 2024*).

The social media influencers have been highly effective in creating awareness of the modest fashion business. Using these influencers, brands can get their products in front of new and receptive followers and create campaigns that feel organic. Modest fashion brands work with influencers to advertise their clothes, and the connection can be achieved by using paid partnerships, free samples for promotional campaigns, and affiliate marketing schemes. This approach has been found to be very effective especially in targeting the younger generation that relies so much on social networks for fashion trends (Usher, 2018).

3.9. *Advancements in Digital Marketing*

Innovations in digital marketing have continued to be the driving force behind advancement within the modest fashion sector. Some of the innovative concepts that are knowledge-intensive include analysing consumers' data and behaviour. This way, the brands can understand their customers better through the acquisition of data by integrating different data sources such as information from e-commerce transactions, social media interactions and different other online touch points that customers engage the brands with. This information helps brands to formulate a targeted marketing approach to better suit the consumer requirements and demands (*The Impact of social media on Modest Fashion, Deenbiscuit, 2024*).

One of the most vital digital tools that have been developed is content marketing. Most companies selling modest wear clothes produce great content in the form of the web post, videos or social media posts to inform and encourage their customers. This type of content is usually very informative and may consist of fashion tips, style tips, and even the author's own story, and this is how many people feel emotionally connected to that brand. For instance, in Haute Hijab's website's blog section, you are likely to find articles such as; 'the extent to which modest fashion has evolved,' 'the reality of being a Muslim woman in the fashion world,' and 'the need to express ourselves through the fashion that we wear' (Benissan, 2022).

Moreover, it is important to note that some minor fashion brands have incorporated the use of AR and VR technologies to improve online buying experiences. Such technologies enable customers to try on products like cloths, visualize how the products would fit, and thus get a better perception of the product. Nevertheless, despite being relatively recent innovative methodologies, the use of AR and/or VR in MM Fashion E-Commerce has the potential to

enhance the customer satisfaction level and minimise return ratios in later phases (Ahmed, 2024).

4. Synthesis and Discussion

The modest fashion industry has been evolving and ascending with popularity and acceptance in international markets, but the consumption structure of this industry reveals challenges and prospects in its development. Awareness of these aspects is critical for brands that desire to operate in the specialist sector. This section focuses on the cultural sensitivity and market segmentation involved in the actualization of the culturally sensitive market segments and will also look at future trends and possible growth prospects that the modest fashion is likely to have.

4.1. *Cultural Relevance and Target Market Niche*

The major drawback of multi-ethnic industry like the modest fashion is that it is often hard to address all the cultural concerns and expectations of people all over the world. Despite sharing some origins in Islamic principles, there are many differences brought about by cultural and regional differences or even individual perceptions of modesty in fashion. For example, things like dressing decently as per the standards of one collective moral code may be seen differently in another. These aspects must be carefully observed by brands as any violation of cultural differences can be considered as cross-cultural incompetence and, therefore, brands have to cater to those specific audiences.

For instance, the Middle Eastern style of the so-called ‘modest fashion’ tends to focus on elegant materials the over-elaborate ornamentation, as the Middle East culture is unconsciously associated with luxury. Thus, while European compatriots might appreciate and prefer elaborate and conforming modest garments, Southeast Asian countries may prefer more comfortable and relaxed attire, appropriate for the climate and the way of life. Such nuances can be useful for avoiding controversies and creating products that would cater to the local population’s peculiarities and preferences (Slater & Demangeot, 2021).

However, it is worth pointing out that the concept of Modest Fashion applies not only to Muslim dominant nations. In Western markets, HK and Ready to Wear are now moving beyond the core Muslim consumers/custom base and increasingly appealing to the larger non-Muslim consumer-base who are embracing modest fashion due to the societal and environmental concerns of fashionable dressing. The brands attracting such audiences must ensure that while adopting the principles of ‘modest fashion,’ they also incorporate aspects of

today's common modern elegant fashion. This mandates analysis of contemporary global fashion trends in apparel and styles them in modesty suitable for the Islamic fashion without loss of its inherent values (Deniz *et al.*, 2023).

4.2. *Multivariate techniques in Market Segmentation and New Venture Targeting*

Market segmentation is a crucial element that brands in the modest fashion industry need to adopt especially if they are targeting different groups of consumers. This involves paradigmatic segmentation where the company defines market segments that are most appropriate to capture by grouping consumers into segments based on variables like age, gender, culture, and lifestyle. For example, young people may be more inclined to buy new savage, aesthetic, and suitable for gorgeous shots on Instagram, while older people may be more interested in timeless, modern styles. It is beneficial for brands to understand these segments since to effectively apply brand value across various segments, the product offering, and promotional strategies must be specific to address requirements and tastes (Elverina & Furinto, 2021).

The best approach to facilitating such segments is the use of effective marketing strategies that can address the segments uniquely. Demographic data, psychographic images and the purchasing behaviour analysis are some of the typical data brands utilize to develop buyer personas. These profiles are of great assistance in the creation of marketing strategies that are deemed suitable for groups of people. For instance, Instagram and TikTok are prominent social media platforms that are used by younger consumers to engage in; therefore, they are the best platforms to use if one wants to promote trendy modest fashion. At the same time, multiple platforms that can be associated with conventional marketing approaches might work better in targeting older individuals, for instance, magazines or community events (Elverina & Furinto, 2021).

Also, there are cases where some brands choose to cover several segments through multiple segment coverage where they launch products targeting the various segments. For instance, it may well establish both a premium product line focusing on wealthy buyers, and a mass production line targeting youthful and middle-aged men and women. This strategy is useful to reach greatest market penetration and thus brands could create a wider customer appeal, increasing its market immersion and revenue streams.

4.3. Future trends and potential growth areas

The modest fashion industry will always be gradually changing with the influence of general fashion trends, fashion technology, progress, and shifting consumer trends. Some new directions that have been noted to be emerging are sustainability and ethical fashion. Thanks to the rising awareness of the environmental issue of the consumers today, a niche market appears to act as the modern movement known as the sustainable fashion, the principle of which is to use the ethic and environmental canons: the use of environmentally friendly fabrics, the disclosure of the principles of fair trade, and the minimization of the use of the so-called endof-roll cuttings. Those brands which act accordingly the above stated values are properly positioned to secure devoted customers and position themselves in a better place as compared to others in the market (Purba, 2024).

Another large trend is the technological element which is gradually becoming a part of fashion. Introduced ideas of augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) and show how they can be used by the brands of the modest fashion. Such technologies enable customers to take virtual fitting trials on the outfit and make better decisions regarding a particular product. Such technologies can also assist brands in lowering the return rates and enhancing the customer satisfaction (Ike, 2024). The appearance of influencer marketing and social networks as a promotion tool can also be noted in the development of the modest fashion niche. Young people and celebrities, that match the characteristics of the modest fashion niche, are the main trendsetters. The use of influencers in the marketing of brands is on the rise for the purpose of marketing, expanding market reach and establishing credibility. It has also been predicted that the involvement of influencers is set to increase even further in the marketing of the modest fashion (Karakavak & Özbölük, 2022).

4.4. Premises for development and innovation

The opportunities for improving the industry and growing in terms of the apparel productions, marketing and using the enhanced technology seems to be vast in modest fashion. One potential is in the creation of unique clothes that will portray Islamic conservatism but in the modern fashion style. Following these aspects, it could be stated that the brands that can manage these factors are likely to attract both functional and symbolic consumers, buyers of both modest and mainstream fashion (Codilla & Aisha, 2021). There is also a possibility of growth that is related to emergent markets, especially where Muslim population is growing fast. A good example is

the case of Southeast Asia which is recording increased demands for the modest fashion due to youthful and fashion-savvy populations. Thus, brands that invest in such markets and products can benefit from this continually growing requirement and solidify its position in the industry. Also, large population acceptor Muslim countries in some developed nations like USA and UK will portray immense market opportunity for modest fashion brands.

In addition, use of digital technologies points to another major direction that has immense potential for innovation at a fundamental level. Big data analytics help brands to understand the consumers better and thus help them in decision making in respect of designing the product and its placement in the market. The application of artificial intelligence helps to improve the experience of the purchase of goods and services through recommendation systems. All these technologies could go a long way in increasing sales and level of customers' satisfaction as espoused by Ike, (2024).

Thus, it can be stated that while the already mentioned problems are real challenges of the industry, the modest fashion market can become the country's potential leader for brands ready to respond to the new market trends. Therefore, manufacturers can position themselves well for long-term development in this flourishing sector by considering cultural taboos, market differentiation, and new opportunities and technologies.

4.5. Insights from Contemporary Muslim Civilization

Modest fashion industry has strong connection with modern Islamic world where religious leaders and thinkers have the major influence on the fashion regulation and trends. Besides, the combination of Islamic values with modernity indicates that this business has a different outlook on entrepreneurship in this sector. This section discusses these dynamics in terms of the role played by religious institutions and scholars and the role of traditional and modern conceptions of commerce and enterprise.

4.5.1 Religious Institutions and Scholars

The role of religious bodies and scholars is critical in determining and shaping the code of dressing within Islamic fashion. They explain scriptures and offer directions that impact the production and promotions of clothes that meet the Islamic standards. These guidelines are relative and can differ from culture to culture and from the perspective of different schools of Islamic law. For example, Islamic scholars from different schools of thought may hold different

opinions about what is considered shameful and appropriate clothing attire, and this may impact the styles and types of clothing considered acceptable (Radwan *et al.*, 2019).

In some Muslim-majority countries, there are institutions with formal mechanisms to regulate and promote modest fashion. For example, in Indonesia, the government promotes Muslim fashion festival shows and exhibitions that adhere to Muslim modest fashion. This endorsement not only legitimizes fashion events but also reassures consumers about their adherence to their values (Yaqub, 2024).

Moreover, well-known scholars' opinion can also contribute to the shift in trends within the niche and limited fashion sector. Their recommendations or condemnation of styles could make individuals change their choices. For example, scholars advocating for more conservative styles can push for less tight and more concealing styles. On the other hand, people who embrace more liberal thought processes might be willing to accept a wider variety of styles, thus increasing the market and the amount of creativity within the business.

4.5.2. Contributions to the Development of Modest Fashion

Muslim scholars and organizations also play a role in the advancement of modest fashion by discussing with the designers and fashion companies. This collaboration helps to ensure that the products that are being marketed and produced are in congruence with the Muslim culture and standards. For example, some fashion companies hire scholars to create clothing lines that are fashionable and Shariah-compliant. This consultation process may include deliberations on fabrics, their placements, designs, and the general outlook of the apparel (*Halal Modest Fashion, ISA, 2023*).

In addition to their employment in the fashion industry, scholars also participate in educational projects. Some scholars are directly engaged in establishing academic programs and courses that revolve around Islamic fashion and design. These programs are to prepare future designers and industry professionals to understand the concepts of modest fashion based on Islamic values combined with modern day design. This educational approach assists in the development of a new generation of designers who understand the principles of Islamic design and are capable of fashion designing at the same time.

4.5.3. The Role of Tradition in the Integration of Present-Day Entrepreneurial Approaches

The modest fashion industry is a perfect example of the merger of Islamic culture and values with the contemporary approaches to entrepreneurship. This balance is important for brands

that wish to attain a universal appeal but do not want to offend any cultural or religious beliefs of the people. A major problem that these brands face is the ability to portray the religious and cultural aspects of the Muslim faith in the eyes of their consumers while at the same time providing modern and trendy clothes (Abdulai *et al.*, 2024).

This can be achieved by maintaining a balance between the business goals and the ethical norms that are expected of a Muslim businessperson. For instance, most of the brands in this category have a clear focus on the supply chain, labour standards, and materials sourcing. All these practices are in accordance with Islamic teachings on justice, fairness, and respecting the dignity of man. According to Abdulai *et al.* (2024) by aligning to these values, brands can gain credibility and consumers' loyalty since these practices are significant to their consumers' self-identity.

Furthermore, most brands of modest fashion clothes do not use embarrassing marketing techniques since they respect different cultures. For instance, the advertisement slogans, symbols, or pictures that may be deemed as unappreciable or provocative to the Islamic culture or the Islamic religion are not depicted in the advertising campaigns. This sensitivity is well captured in the portrayal of women in advertisements, where the emphasis is on decent and respect. Much as such marketing strategies align with the cultural and religious sensitivity of the Muslim consumer, they also appeal to the general consumer who is now more conscious of ethical and appropriate dressing (*Ethical Advertising: Aligning Marketing with Islamic Values - Tazkiyah*, 2024).

Some of the brands and businesspeople in the modest fashion industry have been able to incorporate the Islamic values with the modern business world. A perfect example is the brand known as "Haute Hijab" which was started by Melanie Elturk. The brand provides fashionable hijabs and modest clothes for women who want to follow the religious rules and stay fashionable. The strength of Haute Hijab is in its focus on quality and design while promoting the Islamic way of doing business such as sourcing and marketing that is diverse and inclusive.

Another example is the UK based modest fashion brand 'Aab' which has received international attention. Aab aims at offering nice and trendy Muslimah clothing that complies with the Islamic dress code. The success of the brand has been due to its focus on quality, ethical manufacturing and the ability to appeal to a broad, international market. Aab's business model shows how culture and tradition can be incorporated in the modern fashion, trends, and

practices, thus catering to the diverse consumer base across different cultures (*CASE STUDY- London Modest Fashion Brand Aab Eyes Aggressive Expansion Plan*, 2019).

Furthermore, “Modanisa”, an online based company selling modest fashion has been able to benefit from the shift in technology to sell its products to the world. The platform has a wide range of clothing from different designers which makes it convenient for consumers who are looking for fashionable and modest clothing. The strategic management is focused on the availability of the product and on the target consumers since Modanisa relies on e-commerce and digital marketing to reach out to the customers. This approach does not only fit into the cultural norms of dressing modestly as a virtue but also fits into the modern world of technology (*Modanisa: The Transformative Power of Modest Fashion*, 2020).

So, based on the facts discussed above, we may say that the modest fashion business is a relatively a profound concept that has its origin from the Islamic world and thus combines the ancient culture with the modern economy. There is an undeniable involvement of religious bodies and scholars in fashion as far as setting standards and trends are concerned, while brands are left to grapple with the issues of entrepreneurship in the contemporary world. Thus, the examples of Haute Hijab, Aab, and Modanisa show that it is possible to respect the Islamic canons and be successful in the global fashion business. This balance is not only the secret of mercantile prosperity, but also the evidence of the modern development of the Islamic civilization.

5. Conclusions, implications and limitations

In this section, we draw conclusions based on the preceding discussions, namely, the comparison of entrepreneurial approaches in the sphere of the modest fashion industry and in other sectors and the impact of globalization. Moreover, we discuss the recommendations for relevant industry stakeholders and policymakers and their contribution to the development of the emerging and still quite niche field of modest fashion.

Like any other industry, modest fashion also applies certain business strategies, but it has its own features that are influenced by cultural and religious factors. A major similarity across industries is the focus on innovation and flexibility considering global markets. For example, companies operating in the niche of modest fashion, just like the ones operating in the general fashion industry, have started expanding the use of online spaces and social media. This strategy supports that the digital transformation is one of the crucial success factors in the contemporary entrepreneurial environment.

Nevertheless, the modest fashion industry differs from other industries as it has its own set of ethical and cultural norms. While other fashion industries offer products that are mainly based on appearance and trends, the modest fashion business requires an understanding of religious requirements and cultural norms. Such factors affect the product development process, the promotional campaigns, and the sourcing strategies. For instance, the clothes of modest fashion have the following aspects: Ethical sourcing and production, which are aligned with the Islamic values of fairness and sustainability. This combination of religious compliance and business skills sets the industry apart and presents a specialized market that is less sensitive to the volatility frequently seen in the fashion industry.

5.1 . The impact of globalization on modest fashion compared to other industries

Consequently, the rise of globalization has affected the modest fashion industry in a way that is not entirely similar to other industries. Contrary to other industries, which commonly tend to assimilate cultures and customers' preferences through globalization, the modest fashion industry can be said to have undergone a form of 'selective globalization'. This is a phenomenon that is apparent by the fact that people embrace the modern trends of dressing from other parts of the world while at the same time embracing their cultural and religious beliefs. For instance, while the global fashion trends and standards are quite different, the concept of modest fashion takes those trends and translates them in a way that is more appropriate to Islamic standards to ensure that they retain their individuality in this global fashion market.

In addition, the geographical spread of the modest fashion business is not only about the targeting of new markets but also about the promotion of cultural exchange. Through cultural branding, brands act as representatives of Islamic civilization, which helps to spread tolerance and counter prejudice. This role is less expressed in other industries because the emphasis of most industries is not on cultural representation but on the possibility of profit-making. And this dual role of economic participation and cultural representation makes the Modest Fashion Industry an interesting niche in the era of globalization.

5.2. Implications for Policy and Practice

5.2.1. Recommendations for Industry Stakeholders

Modest fashion is challenging but opens opportunities for a range of stakeholders such as the entrepreneurs, investors, and designers. However, for the stakeholders to fully harness on the

potential growth of the industry, they need to embrace the authenticity in this industry and respect for the cultural values. This requires a clear analysis of the various cultural and religious perspectives wherein modesty fashion exists. For instance, brands should consult with local people and Islamic authorities to reassure themselves and the markets that their products are Sharia compliant and culturally appropriate.

Moreover, it is recommended that stakeholders dedicate funds towards digitalization as it plays a key function in reaching current and prospective customers. This investment entails establishing sound electronic commerce systems, the use of social media for advertisement, and crowd analysis for customer trends. As mentioned, digitalization is not only good for operationalization; it also gives insights into the new trends and customers' preferences. Another recommendation is the fostering of cross-sector cooperation. Partnerships can enhance cooperation in terms of sharing resources, information, and market experiences, which will complement the growth of the modest fashion brands in the market. They could also include partnerships with other sectors within the fashion industry and with other industries in general with the aim of reaching out to more consumers and diversifying the concept of modesty in fashion.

5.2.2. Public policy for the industry

In the modest fashion industry, policymakers are obligated to create an environment that will facilitate industry growth. Thus, one of the primary areas of concern should be the establishment and implementation of necessary rules and standards aimed at promoting ethical approaches in the industry. This includes fair labour standards, use of sustainable materials, and protection of intellectual property. Policy makers should also give incentives to organizations to adopt such an ethical standard, for instance the tax rebates or grants.

Furthermore, there are also other ways through which governments can contribute to the development of the industry and one of them involves the opening of international market access. This support could involve lobbying for multilateral trade policies that lower tariffs on simple fashion products or offer a venue for local fashion manufacturers to market their exports globally. Measures like these would not only aid the growth of domestic players but also contribute to increasing the visibility of brands in the relatively new and small niche of modest fashion.

One domain that policymakers can play the most prominent parts is educational activities. Policies that encourage the setup of training centres, and educational facilities on

Modest Fashion design and enterprise development enhance a pool of competent experts well equipped to help propel the Modest Fashion industry forward. Such programs can also entail components on digital marketing, global business, and cultural relations, which would prepare the future leaders of the industry for the challenges awaiting them in the globalized economy. In addition, it is recommended for policymakers to first consult with industry players to discuss issues concerning market classification and cultural factors. Through the engagement of government, industry stakeholders, and authorities of Islamic law, policymakers can ensure that the legal requirements that apply to the modest fashion industry are sensitive to the cultural orientation of the countries where the industry operates.

In a brief, the modest fashion industry occupying the space where religion, culture, and commerce meet, can be viewed as a specific example of globalization's influence on specialized markets. Like many other sectors, it has similar business tactics, but it is more committed to ethical and cultural values. The conclusion is that there are significant implications for policy and practice, which require greater authenticity, collaboration, and supportive regulations. With the current trends in globalization affecting markets around the world, the modest fashion industry stands to help foster cultural exchange and business growth.

5.3. Key Findings

The analysis of the globalization of the sector of the modest fashion has revealed a number of significant factors that shape it today. One of the areas that this work finds a significant impact from globalization is the modest fashion industry. The concept of 'globalization' has also given rise to brands providing 'modest fashion' clothes to enter the international market. This diversification has been made possible by the internet and the social media platforms that have created a platform for businesses to communicate with the consumers across the world. Therefore, the concept of the modest fashion movement has transitioned from being a fleeting fad to a phenomenon that exists across the globe that attracts a wide variety of consumers depending on their beliefs or feelings, religious, or cultural.

Another major finding is the role played by the entrepreneurs in the emergence and growth of the Modest Fashion industry. The companies in this sector have also been able to show an awareness of market trends and the needs and wants of the customers and have also embraced the concept of branding through innovation. For instance, the employment of e-commerce and digital marketing strategies has been significant in expanding the customer base and expanding into the global market. In addition, buyers are gradually shifting their focus to

the values that are inherent in the purchased goods – this may be considered as the result of the growing concern of the public with the issues of environmental and ethical compatibility. The research also aimed to find out the role of Islamic values and principles in the context of the emerging modest fashion industry. This has affected the kind of products and how these are marketed to conform to the Islamic laws on dressing code among the Muslim civilians. Furthermore, religious authorities and religious organizations have also endorsed and guided the fashion trends, providing authenticity and approval to modest fashion brands than the conventional fashion brands.

5.4. Conclusion

The notion of ‘modest fashion’ within the context of globalization can be considered as one of the signs of the industry’s versatility and stability. On this note, the emergence of modest fashion reflects the diversification of fashion and the growing trend of ethical consumption in contemporary society. Therefore, it can be realized that the sector requires the real and innovative approaches to overcome the challenges posed by globalization and yet retain cultural and religious appeal. As such, the future of modest fashion is bright and holds the promise of significant development in the future. The growing interest in this area, which originates not only from the Muslim world but also from the multicultural and multifaith population, presents a great opportunity for companies. However, there are challenges like cultural distortion and commercialization of religious symbols that threaten the central theme and goal of the modest fashion.

The intertwining of modest fashion with Islamic culture provides opportunities and challenges for stakeholders within the industry. The brands are also still expected to be ethical and engage in processes that are humility, environmentally sensitive as well as socially responsible. With this commitment, modest fashion brands will be able to stand out in the overly saturated market, while ensuring that the industry brings an overall positive impact to the culture and religion.

Therefore, globalization of modest fashion is a cultural, economic and religious process. It is an emerging market that has been initiated by businesspersons and supports the Islamic culture making it a key player in the fashion world. It will be important and developing in the future because the industry describes and defines the process of globalization, the place of culture and religion in the world, and the role of business.

5.5. Limitations of the Study

Despite the findings of this study, there are limitations that are worth acknowledging when discussing the globalization of modest fashion. The research primarily examines the influence of globalization on entrepreneurship and Islamic values in the modest fashion business, which presents a notable constraint. This focused emphasis limits to the study of other variables that may have an impact on the business, such as political or economic contexts.

The approach used in the study; the systematic literature review is comprehensive, but it is limited by the literature published on the topic and the quality of the studies available. The weakness of using secondary research is that certain aspects of the industry development may be omitted particularly the new trends and improvements. Additionally, the studies are mainly carried out in regions where the notion of the concept of modest fashion is appropriate, such as the Middle Eastern and Southeast Asian countries. This focus also creates a bias of what is happening in the industry and leaves out the challenges and possibilities of the small fashion brands operating in the other parts of the globe.

Therefore, future research should seek to incorporate a higher number of factors which may influence the development of the modest fashion industry. It would be more appropriate to use questionnaires and interview the players in the industry as a method of carrying out qualitative research and gain better insight on the current trends. In addition, cross-sectional studies between different geographic regions and cultures could present a broader view on the concepts and implementation of modest fashion globally.

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